

The current systematic review protocol follows the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis Protocols (PRISMA-P) guidelines developed by Moher et al. (2015) and Shamseer et al. (2015).

Section I - Administrative information

Title

Empirical research on masculinity in prisons: protocol for a systematic literature review

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Contributions

VC is the guarantor. VC drafted the protocol. All authors contributed to the development of the selection criteria, the risk of bias assessment strategy, and data extraction criteria. All authors developed the search strategy. All authors read, provided feedback, and approved the final version of the protocol.

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Section II - Introduction

Rationale

More than 10.35 million people are held in penal institutions throughout the world, of which 93.2% are men (Walmsley, 2016). Prisons represent “an ultramasculine world where nobody talks about masculinity” (Sabo et al., 2001, p. 3), although there may be some evidence that prison masculinities are shifting (Maycock, 2023). Aiming at both punishing and rehabilitating prisoners, prisons are a fruitful environment for the reproduction of a hypermasculinity culture (Seymour, 2018), forcing prisoners to display attitudes and behaviours that struggle with their own views of the self, creating cognitive dissonance (Whitehead, 2005). In fact, prisoners live in a particular culture of masculinity, where it is expected that men show physical strengths and authority, take care of their problems, are willing to fight, demonstrate the capacity for combat, and have the ability to “display transcendental courage” (Schouten, 2011; Toch, 1998; Whitehead, 2005, p. 414). The issues of power and masculinity, particularly in male prisons, represent the “most violently contested psychological terrain” (Haney, 2011, p. 121). Within this culture, the rejection of all things feminine and the display of coherent heterosexuality is necessary but not sufficient to prove one’s masculinity. Moreover, one needs to distance himself from homosexuality through homophobic behaviour (Alsop et al., 2002). Masculinity can be seen as a dynamic risk factor of violent behavior (Whitehead, 2005), meaning that it increases the propensity for

violence, but also that it can be changed through interventions, reducing future violent recidivism (Klepfisz et al., 2016). In fact, violence between men usually occurs in one of the two following scenarios (Whitehead, 2005): (1) affirmation of the perpetrator's masculinity by a display of courage against a rival man, including the victim in the category "man" as a worthy rival (inclusive violence); (2) excluding the victim from the category "man", using violence as a means to humiliate and/or feminise the victim (exclusive violence). Therefore, violence and aggression serve the purpose of showing that the perpetrator is not the "Non-man". Being both inclusive and exclusive, in a prison environment, violence can represent a baseline social answer for daily situations. While part of the prison culture, violence and hypermasculinity reach their peak at relatively young ages (Toch, 1998). However, despite the known correlation between cultural constructions of masculinity and crime, the development of efficient interventions for inmates, and particularly for young inmates, in order to help them "redefine masculinity in a way that will help them succeed" has been neglected (Karp, 2010, p. 68).

Objectives

The aim of this systematic review is **to review empirical quantitative and qualitative literature on masculinity in prisons, describing, organising/presenting the results to inform future research, policy, and practice**. The authors will examine the most frequently studied outcomes and co-variables to identify attitudes and experiences that receive the most scholarly attention, as well as those who might need further attention from researchers.

Section III - Methods

Eligibility criteria

The authors will consider the following studies as eligible:

Regarding study design: the authors will consider all studies reporting the results of empirical research eligible. Thus, quantitative study designs, including descriptive,

correlational, causal-comparative, and experimental, and qualitative methods, such as case studies, ethnographic studies, and grounded theory research, will be considered.

Regarding participants: the authors will include studies with all types of participants. This might include (but are not limited to) prison officers and prison staff in general (of any gender), and prisoners that identify as men (independently of age). Former prisoners will not be considered.

Regarding setting: the authors will only consider studies that took place in youth justice facilities, prisons, and jails. All studies developed in other settings (e.g., therapeutic communities, schools, migrant detention centres, community) will be excluded.

Regarding Language: the authors will consider studies written in English, Portuguese, Spanish, French, and Dutch.

Regarding document type: articles, conference proceedings, books, book chapters, master's dissertations, and doctoral theses will be considered. All other document types (e.g., reviews, editorials, notes) will be excluded. Unpublished materials and abstracts will not be considered.

Regarding years of publication: no restrictions will be applied. Although the authors expect that most studies will be developed in the last years/decades, studies published in any year will be considered.

Regarding geographical location: there are no geographical restrictions, and thus studies from all locations will be included.

Information Sources

All authors performed an exploratory search with a search query on several search systems considered as appropriate for systematic literature reviews (cf. Gusenbauer & Haddaway, 2020). Consistent results among all authors were observed in the following databases, that will therefore be used in the current study: SCOPUS; Web of Science; Proquest, Pubmed; and Wiley Online Library. These search systems include the biggest databases available (i.e. SCOPUS and Web of Science), as well as other databases (i.e. Proquest, Pubmed; and Wiley Online Library) that will allow us to reach an inclusive list of studies.

Search Strategy

Following exploratory searches on different search systems, the authors agreed on the use of the following keywords:

prison*

jail*

correction*

mascul*

manliness

maleness

manfulness

manhood

virility

These keywords allow us to construct a search query that is adapted to the different search systems, considering the requirements of the advanced search. The following search queries will be used:

SCOPUS: TITLE-ABS (prison* OR jail* OR correction*) AND TITLE-ABS (mascul* OR manliness OR maleness OR manfulness OR manhood OR virility)

Web of Science: TS = (prison* OR jail* OR correction*) AND TS = (mascul* OR manliness OR maleness OR manfulness OR manhood OR virility)

Proquest: ABSTRACT(prison* OR jail* OR correction*) AND ABSTRACT(mascul* OR manliness OR maleness OR manfulness OR manhood OR virility)

Pubmed: ((prison*[Title/Abstract] OR jail*[Title/Abstract] OR correction*[Title/Abstract])) AND ((mascul*[Title/Abstract] OR manliness[Title/Abstract] OR maleness[Title/Abstract] OR manfulness[Title/Abstract] OR manhood[Title/Abstract] OR virility[Title/Abstract]))

Wiley Online Library: (prison* OR jail* OR correction*) AND (mascul* OR manliness OR maleness OR manfulness OR manhood OR virility)

Study records

Data management

After performing the searches on the different databases, references' titles and abstracts will be exported in .ris format and imported into Zotero. A Zotero group will be created, and all authors will have access to it. Different folders will be created for the results of each database. Duplicates will be removed using the corresponding function in Zotero. An excel file will be created with a list of all references, and an ID will be assigned to each reference. This will help us randomly assign the references to the different authors that will screen the results. After the selection process takes place, the included references will be organised in a separate folder, and the full text of all studies will be added.

Selection process

The authors will independently screen the search results' titles and abstracts against the inclusion criteria. This will be done in such a way that every result is screened by at least 2 authors. For every result that meets the inclusion criteria, or in cases where there is any doubt, each author will register a decision (include, exclude, or unclear). When more information is required to address eligibility concerns, we will access the full text at this stage and contact the study authors if needed. When there is any disagreement (i.e. author decisions do not match), all authors will screen the title/abstract and decisions will be made by consensus.

Data collection process

A data extraction table was created to facilitate the collection of information we want from each study (see Appendix A). The table includes:

Information about the article: citation in APA format (author, year).

Information about the study: design, number of participants, type of participants, age, country.

Variable of interest (i.e. masculinity): definition, measure, manifestations (e.g., competition, stoicism, homophobia).

Outcomes / co-variables: definition and measure. Due to the aims of this systematic review and inclusion criteria, we do not expect every study included in the analysis to have a clear outcome or co-variable, namely in the qualitative studies and in the quantitative studies with a descriptive design. However, when included studies consider outcomes and co-variables we will consider all variables that are related to masculinity. This can include stress, anxiety, help-seeking intentions, trauma, prison violence, and male rape.

Main results: synthesis of the main results. This can include the relationships between study variables in the case of quantitative studies.

Studies will be randomly assigned to each researcher, and data extraction will be performed individually. Every time data extraction is carried out by one researcher, another member of the research team will verify it. Any inconsistencies will be discussed.

Assessment of quality / risk of bias

The authors will use the corresponding critical appraisal tools available at JBI (Joanna Briggs Institute; <https://jbi.global/critical-appraisal-tools>), depending on the type of study being assessed, to assess the risk of bias (at study level).

Qualitative synthesis

The authors' planned systematic review will provide a narrative synthesis in the text and table(s). Information might be divided considering the study type. This means that a narrative synthesis of qualitative research can be presented first, followed by a narrative synthesis of quantitative research. Table(s) will be used to present information about the type of study (quantitative or qualitative), sample size and characteristics, country where the study was conducted, setting, method, measures (if applicable), and main results, taking into account the number of studies to be synthesised.

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Appendix A

Table 1 - Data extraction table sample

Citation	Study Design	Participants (N, age, profile)	Country of study	Study variables	Measures	Main results